

Health Risk Prediction for Children Built on a Combination of Heterogeneous Datasets

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Abstract—Health risk prediction tools for children are important to identify those at risk in order to start timely interventions. However, they currently do not exist, so the SmartCHANGE project is developing cardiometabolic health risk prediction models for children and youth. This is a difficult task because there are no datasets tracking individuals from childhood to sufficiently old age with an appreciable disease prevalence. We, therefore, combine longitudinal and cross-sectional datasets containing different risk factors. We fill out the datasets with missing variable values by imputation, and by predicting variables that are missing in some datasets from the variables in overlaps between datasets. This enables the prediction of risk factors up to age 55. At that age, we feed the risk factors into existing risk prediction models for cardiovascular disease and diabetes. Given the nature of the problem and the available data, it is difficult to evaluate whether the resulting risks are correct, but preliminary results indicate they are reasonable.

Index Terms—incomplete data, limited label access, real-world applications, life-long learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Statistical and even machine-learning tools for predicting health risk are increasingly established, especially for cardiovascular risk – many health professionals, for example, use the SCORE2 model [1] developed by the European Society of Cardiology. However, such models for children do not exist. This is because the non-communicable diseases these models are predicting are far in the future for most of them, so developing risk-prediction tools is technically difficult, and the need does not appear great. However, health behaviors that eventually lead to disease begin at a young age, and even physical disease precursors are evident in some cases. Evidence points to childhood and adolescence as an ideal period for risk-lowering strategies based on behavior modification [2]. Identifying children who should be targeted by such strategies is surprisingly difficult, though. This is why the SmartCHANGE project [3] is developing a model and tools for predicting cardiometabolic risk for children and youth.

To predict the risk of non-communicable diseases for children, one would ideally want a dataset that contains a broad range of risk factors going from a young age (when we want to make the prediction) to an old age (when the diseases typically occur) for the same individuals. However, compiling such a dataset would require tracking many people over many decades. Consequently, ideal datasets for our purpose do not exist, however, many relevant datasets for risk prediction do exist. Our objective is to combine such heterogeneous datasets

in order to build a risk prediction model. In this paper, we describe the first attempt at this, in which we use four datasets. We identify their overlaps, sometimes by generalizing some variables. We then use models trained on these overlaps to generate synthetic values for datasets that do not contain certain variables, similar to some imputation approaches. We use this completed dataset to forecast some of the variables – the risk factors – in middle age. We finally feed these risk factors into established models designed to predict the 10-year risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we briefly review related work on risk prediction models, imputation and synthetic data generation. In Section III, we present the datasets used in the paper. In Section IV, we proceed to describe our risk prediction modeling pipeline, followed by the results in Section V. With Section VI, we conclude the paper and provide some ideas for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Several risk scores were developed and are currently used for predicting cardiovascular risk [1], [4]–[6] and diabetes [7]. Some of the most popular scores were developed and validated even on multiple cohorts [1], [8]. However, these cohort datasets are homogeneous in the sense that they contain all the variables of interest at ages of interest. This means that predicting risk from them is relatively straightforward, whereas in our case each dataset is different and not sufficient to predict risk on its own.

Imputation of missing data is a crucial step for robust predictive models in health studies. A common approach to imputation is joint modeling, which specifies a multivariate distribution for all variables, but can be complex to implement with diverse datasets. Fully Conditional Specification, on the other hand, imputes missing data using a series of univariate conditional models. This method is more flexible than joint modeling, but may face theoretical limitations due to potential model incompatibility [9].

Synthetic data generation similarly plays a significant role in medical research, primarily addressing challenges related to data privacy and scarcity. Generative Adversarial Networks and Variational Autoencoders are popular methods for generating synthetic data. These methods are particularly useful for creating synthetic data that maintains complex relationships between variables, however, such methods also require large

TABLE I
SELECTED DATASETS

Name	SLOfit	LGS	YFS	AFINA-TE
Origin	SI	BE	FI	PT
Age range	5 - 20	5 - 25	0 - 60	5 - 25
Longitudinal	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Num. of people	280165	17991	3596	1632
Num. of measurements	3121399	31127	32364	1632
Num. of variables	13	80	24	59
Missing values	2.55%	16.25%	39.49%	33.53%

TABLE II
PRESENCE OF VARIOUS VARIABLES OF INTEREST ACROSS SELECTED DATASETS

Attributes	SLOfit	LGS	YFS	AFINA-TE
Age	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sex	✓	✓	✓	✓
Height	✓	✓	✓	✓
Weight	✓	✓	✓	✓
Waist circumference		✓	✓	✓
Fitness	✓	✓		✓
Resting heart rate		✓	✓	✓
Systolic blood pressure		✓	✓	✓
Diastolic blood pressure		✓	✓	✓
Glucose				✓
Total cholesterol			✓	✓
HDL			✓	✓
LDL			✓	✓
Physical activity		✓	✓	✓
Smoking		✓	✓	
Diet			✓	

amounts of data for training, which can be difficult to obtain [10]–[12].

III. DATA

The datasets used in this work are presented in Table I. From the datasets we decided to keep specific 16 variables, either because they are incorporated into the existing risk prediction models we utilize or because they are essential for establishing connections between datasets; the presence of variables in each of the datasets is shown in the Table II.

The SLOfit dataset is a dataset based on a school-based fitness monitoring program in Slovenia for children aged 6 to 19. It aims to improve physical education by systematically evaluating students’ physical development, supported by national school legislation. Schools annually measure body height, weight, triceps, skinfold thickness, and motor abilities through eight fitness tests [13].

The Leuven Growth Study of Belgian Boys [14] dataset (LGS) was obtained between 1969 and 1974, with the aim of describing the physical fitness of Belgian boys aged 12 to 18 and gathering longitudinal data on their growth. Measurements include physical growth, biological maturity, motor performance, sports practice, and sociocultural characteristics.

The Leuven Growth Study of Flemish Girls dataset (also abbr. LGS) [15] was obtained from 1979 to 1980. Its focus was the assessment of the physical fitness of Flemish girls aged 6 to 18. Data collected includes physical fitness tests, anthropometric measures, somatotype ratings, biological maturity,

sociocultural factors, sports skills, sports practice, hygiene, and eating habits.

The Cardiovascular Risk in Young Finns Study dataset (YFS) [16] is a collection of measurements from 1980 to 2020, with the aim of exploring early cardiovascular disease risk factors in youth. The data includes measurements of children, but also of adults, at later numerous follow-ups. Data collection includes questionnaires, physical measurements, and blood tests, focusing on variables like serum lipoproteins, insulin, inflammation markers, obesity indices, blood pressure, lifestyle factors, and socioeconomic status.

The AFINA-TE dataset [17] is part of an intervention program aimed at promoting physical fitness, activity, and nutritional knowledge among children and adolescents. Conducted in the district of Porto, Portugal, the study involved participants aged 12–18, split into an intervention group and a control group. Data collection included accelerometer measurements of physical activity and the Nutrition Knowledge Questionnaire to assess dietary habits.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Preprocessing

Initially, units of measurements of the same variables were standardized across datasets. Multiple measurements of a single variable at the same measurement point (e.g., systolic blood pressure) were next combined by calculating their mean to provide a consistent single measure. Smoking status codes, which differed between datasets, were aligned. Additionally, in the SLOfit dataset we excluded all data rows that had more than one-third of their attributes missing and then sampled 20,000 unique participants from the dataset. This was possible due to the substantial size of the dataset. The resulting dataset, consisting of 217,843 data points, was consequently more robust and comprehensive.

B. Individual dataset imputation

The imputation of missing values within each dataset was performed uniformly. The initial imputation sweep utilized only fully observed variables, such as height, weight, sex, and age, as features for models used to impute missing values in other variables. Variables were imputed based on the order of their ratios of non-missing values: those having the highest ratio were selected first. Once a variable was imputed during the sweep, it was considered complete and used in subsequent imputations.

The models that we used include Gradient Boosting, Linear, Ridge and Logistic Regression, ElasticNet, Random Forest and Gaussian Process Classifiers. The performance of a model was evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation. For classification models, accuracy was used as the scoring metric, acknowledging the limitations of accuracy for imbalanced datasets. For regression models, mean absolute error (MAE) was used. The model with the best cross-validation performance was then retrained using all available data points of the target variable and employed to predict the missing values.

Fig. 1. Overlap of variables in SLOfit and YFS datasets across the age range. The SLOfit dataset shows a partial overlap of variables with the YFS dataset for certain age ranges. Models are trained on the overlapping variables to predict the variables present in YFS but missing in SLOfit (grey).

While imputation helps to address the issue of missing data, it also carries potential risks. The imputed values may not always accurately represent the true distribution of the data, especially if the missing data is not random. This could lead to biases in the model predictions and reduce how well the results apply to other situations. Moreover, imputed data may introduce artificial correlations between variables, potentially misleading the model’s understanding of genuine relationships. To mitigate these risks, we performed a second sweep to refine the dataset further, training only on each variable’s non-imputed (ground truth) values. In this iteration, all of the input columns were considered complete, utilizing the entire set of variables for imputation. This time, models were trained again using the ground truth values but with the newly imputed values from the first sweep included in the dataset, providing a more comprehensive dataset for the imputation process.

C. Synthetic data generation

At this point all the missing values from each dataset were imputed. However, subjects from different datasets still had different variables. The task of the next step was to generate synthetic data: to predict variables observed in some datasets, but completely unobserved in some other datasets.

To this end we first modified similar variables across different datasets to make them (roughly) equivalent, to achieve greater overlap between the datasets, which in turn resulted in a more precise data generation process. The following variables from SLOfit or LGS datasets were declared equivalent:

- Shuttle run times from the LGS datasets and 60-meter dash from the SLOfit dataset.
- Sitting arm reach measure and the standing bow variable. Bow, in this case, is the subject performing a standing front fold as far as possible.
- Vertical jump and the standing long jump.
- Leg lifts and torso lifting exercise.
- Sum of skinfold and triceps skinfold.

Equivalent variables were next converted to the same scale, namely to z-scores, where the z-score of a variable is defined as $(\text{variable value} - \text{mean}) / \text{standard deviation}$.

Next we combined all the datasets into one large dataset consisting of any overlapping variables and target variables.

Figure 1 illustrates combining SLOfit and YFS datasets. We then repeated the imputation processes as described in section B, though with the already imputed values from the previous section also taken as the ground truth.

D. Individual forecasting

After the generation of synthetic data we obtained a merged dataset with no missing values. This enabled us to train machine learning models capable of forecasting the variables from a childhood to adulthood and to, subsequently, use the forecasts as inputs to the publicly available models for the predictions of health risk. The age of a child was chosen to be 14, a typical age of a child still in school, whereas the age of an adult was selected as 55, the oldest age supported by our data.

The first approach of forecasting the variables works more on an individual level, whereas the second method estimates the distribution of the whole population in order to predict the variables of an individual. In the first approach we decided, since no measurements exist for the same people at ages both 14 and 55, to split the entire forecasting into forecasting from 14 to 18 and then from 18 to 55, for which data is available. Here we implemented two fully connected neural networks, each applied on a separate time frame, with 27 inputs and 26 outputs per network. There is one less output than input, since we are not predicting the person’s sex. Both networks have one hidden layer with 27 neurons, which use the “ReLU” activation function, whereas the output layer uses a linear activation function. During the training of the neural networks we used mean squared error as the loss function.

E. Population-based forecasting

Individual forecasting requires data from the same person from start to end age. While we have some data close to this ideal (Subsection IV-D), we have even more data on different people at different ages, which makes it possible to consider how variable values change over time in whole population. Predictions of future values for a specific person can then be obtained by estimating where in the general population the person should “lie” in the future. Such forecasting is less personalized, but also less susceptible to unexpected behaviors for atypical individuals.

In the first step we choose an age timespan for which we want to forecast the unknown values. We opted for the timespan that starts at the age of 5 and ends at 55 years of age, since these two ages correspond to our earliest and latest measurements. For each variable, we next estimate the initial or crude population means and standard deviations at ages for which we actually have the data. For each such age, we first collect the corresponding measurements. If the number of measurements is too low for a relatively reliable estimation of mean and deviation, we keep including neighboring ages until the criterion of enough observations is achieved. The criterion for a numeric variable is at least 500 measurements, whereas, for the categorical variable, one must collect at least 10 measurements for at least 2 classes (categorical variables can

have very low number counts for some of their classes). At this point we calculate the initial mean and standard deviation of the obtained measurements.

In the next step we smooth the obtained estimates and fill in the missing values at the unknown years with the following procedure. The entire age timespan is split in any possible combination of two or three distinct subintervals, such that they cover the whole timespan. Any combination for which any of the subintervals does not include at least 20 % of age points from the first step is immediately rejected since fitting a function on such a small number of ages will not yield stable approximations. For each remaining combination we next estimate how well it fits the previously obtained means and deviations, by fitting each of the linear, quadratic, exponential, power and logarithmic functions on the intersection of each subinterval with the ages from the first step. The error of the fit of a combination (including the choice of the fitting functions) equals the sum of the absolute errors at all the age points from the first step. Next, we select the combination that achieved the lowest error and estimate the final population means and standard deviations on the whole age timespan.

For a given person we forecast the future values of a given variable via the use of z-scores. Naturally, to “reverse” the z-score value back to the original range, one reverses the order and multiplies the z-score value with standard deviation, and then adds the mean. In order to forecast the future values of a variable at a given “present” time, we first select the most recent three (or less, if the person does not have enough observations) z-scores from the past and average them. We then make a very rough assumption that this person will also have such a z-score in the future. Finally, at a chosen age in the future, we reverse the z-score back to the usual range by using the estimated mean and standard deviation at that age. We decided to only forecast future values based on the last three z-scores because the earlier measurements, in general, are not as relevant as the most recent.

F. Risk prediction

In this study, models SCORE2 and QxMD are employed to assess the risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes. These models are selected due to their robustness and widely recognized efficacy in predicting the likelihood of developing these chronic conditions. Incorporating both SCORE2 and QxMD models allows for a comprehensive evaluation of cardiometabolic risk factors, enabling healthcare practitioners to make informed decisions regarding patient management and intervention strategies.

The Cardio-Vascular Diseases Risk Calculator – SCORE2 [1] model, developed by the European Society of Cardiology, is utilized to estimate the risk of cardiovascular events over a 10-year period. It incorporates variables such as age, sex, smoking status, blood pressure, and lipid profile to calculate the risk score. Additionally, SCORE2 considers regional variations in risk factors to provide more accurate predictions tailored to specific populations.

The Diabetes Risk Calculator – QxMD model [7], a comprehensive tool for clinical decision support, is employed to evaluate the risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus. This model integrates risk factors of age, BMI, family history, physical activity level, and dietary habits.

V. RESULTS

For simplicity, we are presenting results for the variables incorporated in the SCORE2 and QxMD risk prediction model (with minor exceptions, such as the use of steroids, which cannot be predicted properly from the available data). In Table, III, results for imputation and data generation are presented. Variables Height and Weight are included in all datasets and are used as input to predict other variables. With the exception of Smoking, the errors of the remaining variables are not very large. We will consider making Smoking less fine-grained in the future, as the risk prediction models into which we are feeding it actually do not require the kind of granularity we have at the moment.

TABLE III
MEAN ABSOLUTE ERROR FOR IMPUTED DATA AND FOR SYNTHETIC DATA.

	MAE	Rel. Error (%)
Height [cm]	Included in all datasets	
Weight [kg]	Included in all datasets	
SBP [mmHg]	3.92	3.2
Total cholesterol [mmol/L]	0.184	3.5
HDL [mmol/L]	0.082	6.44
LDL [mmol/L]	0.111	3.7
Smoking [1-9]	1.39	41.8

Tables IV and V present results for individual forecasting for age 18 from age 14 and age 55 from age 18, respectively. The errors of the first stage of forecasting are very low, as expected, considering the short time period. The errors of the second stage are higher, but we still judge them relatively low, with most being lower than the errors of the imputation. Smoking is again problematic, while the other variable with a high error is Weight. It is not clear why this is the case, but we hypothesize that many adolescents at age 14 are still undergoing puberty, which is a time of large body changes, making reliable forecasting difficult.

TABLE IV
ERROR METRICS FOR INDIVIDUAL FORECASTING TO AGE 18 FROM AGE 14.

	MAE	Rel. Error (%)
Height [cm]	3.11	1.8
Weight [kg]	4.79	7.3
SBP [mmHg]	1.46	1.3
Total cholesterol [mmol/L]	0.05	1.1
HDL [mmol/L]	0.02	1.5
LDL [mmol/L]	0.05	1.7
Smoking [1-9]	1.01	46.9

In Table VI results for population-based forecasting for age 55 are shown. Most of the errors are larger than with individual forecasting, which is in line with this method being less personalized. Weight is forecast more accurately here,

TABLE V
ERROR METRICS FOR INDIVIDUAL FORECASTING TO AGE 55 FROM AGE 18.

	MAE	Rel. Error (%)
Height [cm]	3.47	2.0
Weight [kg]	13.60	16.6
SBP [mmHg]	2.39	2.0
Total cholesterol [mmol/L]	0.10	2.3
HDL [mmol/L]	0.08	6.1
LDL [mmol/L]	0.17	6.1
Smoking [1-9]	1.72	98.2

though. In the future, we may combine both methods or use the more accurate one for each variable.

TABLE VI
ERROR METRICS FOR POPULATION-BASED FORECASTING UP TO AGE 55.

	MAE	Rel. Error (%)
Height [cm]	1.62	0.9
Weight [kg]	10.58	12.3
SBP [mmHg]	10.91	9.0
Total cholesterol [mmol/L]	0.64	12.2
HDL [mmol/L]	0.21	16.3
LDL [mmol/L]	0.51	16.8
Smoking [1-9]	2.26	67.9

Rigorous evaluation of risk prediction, which is our ultimate objective, requires data on actual disease. While we are in the process of obtaining such data, we currently do not have it, so as a preliminary evaluation, we selected four test persons with different levels of risk. The upper part of Table VII shows their health parameters, which serve as input data. Persons 1 and 2 are healthy, with person 2 having most parameters more desirable, although person 1 is better with respect to HDL cholesterol. Persons 3 and 4 are unhealthy, with person 3 having even less desirable parameters than 4. So the expected risks are Person 2 < Person 1 < Person 4 < Person 3.

The upper part of Table VII shows the risks of the test persons, and Figures 2 and 3 present the probability of developing cardiovascular disease and diabetes, respectively, by using the data generated with population-based forecasting. One can see that the predicted risks are indeed ordered as expected. More specifically, for persons 1 and 2, the cardiovascular risk at a young age is relatively low, less than 0.5%. As they age, their respective risk curves also begin to rise relatively slowly, which is to be expected since those persons are relatively healthy. On the other hand, person 3 and 4 are not healthy at age 14 and already start with the risk of around 2.5% and 1.25%, respectively, moreover, as they age, their poor health increasingly manifests as disease risk, and thus also their respective risk curves start increasing significantly.

Looking at the diabetes risks, we can see that the pattern is roughly repeated. Person 1 and 2 start with a very small risk at the age of 15; moreover, over time, their curves also increase relatively slowly. However, persons 3 and 4 at age 14 already start at a very worrying risk probability at roughly

32% and 11%. Similarly, as in the case of cardiovascular risk, as they age, the risks increase more rapidly for persons 3 and 4 compared to persons 1 and 2. While the onset of diabetes tends to be earlier than that of cardiovascular disease, and so it is appropriate that the diabetes risks are higher, our prediction of diabetes risk is probably too high. A possible explanation is that there are not many people similar to Person 3 and 4 in our datasets, resulting in less accurate prediction. This is partially because much of our data from younger ages was collected several decades ago (otherwise, we could not have data for the same individuals up to age 55), and adolescents at that time were overall healthier than today.

TABLE VII
INPUTS FOR SCORE2 MODEL FOR FOUR PEOPLE AT AGE 14, AND THE PROBABILITY OF DEVELOPING CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE (CVD) AND TYPE 2 DIABETES (T2D) BETWEEN AGES 55 AND 65.

	Person 1	Person 2	Person 3	Person 4
Age	14	14	14	14
Gender	M	F	M	F
BMI	20	19	30	29
SBP	110	107	139	135
Total cholesterol	4.0	3.5	6.0	5.0
HDL	1.5	1.3	1.0	1.0
LDL	2.0	1.5	4.0	3.5
Smoking	Never	Never	Yes	Occasionally
Risk for CVD at 55	3.0 %	2.8 %	18.7 %	11.8 %
Risk for T2D at 55	10.0 %	4.6 %	85.0 %	70.2 %

Fig. 2. 10-year probability of developing cardiovascular disease (CVD) by using data generated with population-based forecasting.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the paper we presented a methodology of health risk prediction for children, which combines multiple heterogeneous datasets with existing risk-prediction models for adults. After preprocessing, we imputed missing data within each dataset. We then combined datasets and generated values of variables that were not present in all datasets from the variables in their overlaps. Afterwards we used two methods for predicting risk factors at age 55 from those at age 14: one that relied on individual data spanning the prediction age range, and a more

Fig. 3. 10-year probability of developing type 2 diabetes by using data generated with population-based forecasting.

general one that relied on population data. Finally we fed the forecast risk factors into SCORE2 and QxMD models for cardiovascular disease and diabetes, respectively.

Our results show that the errors in imputation and synthetic data generation are low, suggesting that even with limited dataset overlaps, the generated data provide a solid foundation for forecasting. The forecasting methods performed well, with the personalized approach showing slightly better accuracy. Although rigorous validation of risk predictions is ongoing, the preliminary results are promising, indicating that our approach could improve the identification of at-risk children beyond current methods such as BMI.

In this work, we relied primarily on biological features common in established risk prediction models, which tend to indicate risk when it is already apparent. Future work will focus more on behavioral features, like diet, physical activity, and fitness, which can signal risk earlier than biological markers. This shift will help us better predict high-risk individuals who appear healthy but engage in risky behaviors that could lead to future health problems.

Moving forward, we will incorporate more datasets, refine our methodology, and conduct a more rigorous evaluation. Our ultimate goal is to develop a comprehensive neural network model that fully leverages all available datasets, which will require innovative architecture and training techniques.

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